

AI-enhanced soil carbon estimation using the nutrient tracking tool (NTT) and APEX model

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Abstract

The growing recognition of soil carbon's crucial role in climate change mitigation has spurred advancements in estimation and monitoring methods. Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) with existing tools like the Nutrient Tracking Tool (NTT) and Agricultural Policy/Environmental eXtender (APEX) model represents a significant development in this domain. This study explores AI's application to enhance soil carbon estimation accuracy, efficiency, and scalability. By leveraging AI, we aim to improve land management practices and environmental sustainability. The integration of AI with NTT and APEX enhances predictive capabilities, facilitating more precise soil carbon assessments crucial for effective carbon management and climate policy implementation.

Keywords: Soil carbon estimation, artificial intelligence, Nutrient Tracking Tool, APEX model, environmental sustainability

Introduction

The increasing recognition of the critical role that soil carbon plays in mitigating climate change has led to significant advancements in the methods used to estimate and monitor soil carbon levels. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) with existing soil carbon estimation tools and models represents a promising development in this field. This paper explores the application of AI in enhancing soil carbon estimation using the Nutrient Tracking Tool (NTT) and the Agricultural Policy/Environmental eXtender (APEX) model. By leveraging AI, we aim to improve the accuracy, efficiency, and scalability of soil carbon estimation, ultimately contributing to better land management practices and environmental sustainability.

Nutrient Tracking Tool (NTT) is an internet application that allows those who are interested in evaluating non-point source runoff from farms to compare various scenarios for nutrient and sediment reduction. Farmers, government officials, researchers, and other users have the ability to assess how different conservation strategies and other scenarios affect nutrient and sediment losses in specific

fields. Effect on crop yields and other important indicators are also provided to the user.

Importance of soil carbon estimation

Soil carbon sequestration is a key component of the global carbon cycle, acting as a significant carbon sink that can mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. Accurate estimation of soil carbon is crucial for understanding carbon dynamics, developing effective carbon management strategies, and implementing climate change mitigation policies. Traditional methods of soil carbon estimation often involve labor-intensive and time-consuming soil sampling and laboratory analysis. While these methods provide valuable data, they are limited in their spatial and temporal coverage. The Environmental Policy Integrated Climate model (EPIC) (Williams, 1990) [38], a field-level model created in the early 1980s to evaluate the impacts of management policies on water quality, was updated to become APEX (Williams *et al.*, 1990) [38]. By enabling the simultaneous modelling of several contiguous subareas (fields) for a variety of soil, landscape, climate, crop rotation, and management practice

combinations, APEX expands the capabilities of EPIC. It may be used for applications that need the setup of at least two subareas, such as filter strip impacts on nutrient losses from manure application fields. It is meant for full farm or small watershed evaluations.

Current tools for soil carbon estimation

The Nutrient Tracking Tool (NTT) and the APEX model are widely used tools for soil carbon estimation. The NTT is a web-based application that simulates the impact of agricultural management practices on nutrient losses and soil carbon levels. The APEX model, on the other hand, is a comprehensive, mechanistic model that simulates the biophysical processes of agricultural landscapes, including soil carbon dynamics. Both tools offer valuable insights into soil carbon sequestration, but they can benefit from the integration of AI to enhance their predictive capabilities.

APEX (version 0604 and above) now includes the carbon fate and transport features of the CENTURY model (Parton, 1996), enabling it to simulate carbon dynamics in the soil-plant system. APEX also has reservoir and groundwater components. You can split a field or small watershed as much as needed to make sure that the soil, land use, management, and other characteristics of each subarea are comparatively uniform. Evaluation of the relationships between subareas including surface runoff, return flow, tile flow, sediment deposition, irrigation, nutrient transfer, and groundwater flow is made possible by the routing methods in APEX.

The role of artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence, particularly machine learning (ML) algorithms, has shown great potential in improving the accuracy and efficiency of environmental modeling. ML algorithms can analyze large datasets, identify complex patterns, and make accurate predictions based on historical data. By integrating AI with the NTT and APEX model, we can enhance their ability to estimate soil carbon levels more accurately and efficiently.

Data collection and preprocessing

The integration of AI with the NTT and APEX model involves several key steps. First, we need to collect a comprehensive dataset that includes soil properties, management practices, weather conditions, and other relevant variables. This dataset will serve as the training data for the ML algorithms. Next, we preprocess the data to remove any inconsistencies or outliers and normalize the variables to ensure they are on the same scale.

Weather Information: 4 KM² resolution precipitation, minimum and maximum temperature records from 1981 to 2017 are accessible across the United States. The USDA Parameter-elevation Regressions on Independent Slopes Model (PRISM) at Oregon State University is the source of the meteorological data. PRISM reports and articles can be seen at <http://prism.oregonstate.edu>. Every year, the weather data is updated to provide the most recent information. For APEX to create all the missing weather data (such as solar radiation), the monthly weather files (MWF) are necessary. NTT also uses the most recent local (PRISM) meteorological data to produce the MWF at the 4-km² grid

for any area of the US mainland and Puerto Rico. As a result, the APEX computations (such ET) are more accurate.

Soil Data: The Soil Survey Geographic (SURGGO) databases of the United States Department of Agriculture's Natural Resources Conservation Service (USDA-NRCS) include information on soil properties such as bulk density, organic carbon, pH, calcium carbonate, and texture. At the moment, NTT maintains a copy of USDA-SURGGO on its website, which may be viewed using its mapping system based on Google. Every year, NTT updates its soil database with the most recent information from the USDA SURGGO webpage.

Lastly, for each kind of soil in the simulated region, the soil routine in NTT computes the soil surface slope (SL) using the 30-m DEM resolution. By averaging the slope for each polygon's cells and the outcome for every kind of soil, the slope is determined.

Machine learning algorithm selection and training

Once the data is preprocessed, we can select and train the ML algorithms. There are various ML algorithms that can be used for soil carbon estimation, including decision trees, random forests, support vector machines, and neural networks. Each algorithm has its strengths and weaknesses, and the choice of algorithm depends on the specific characteristics of the dataset and the desired level of accuracy.

The model sensitivity approach is carried out for the targeted geographic area in order to identify the most crucial factors that need to be taken into account throughout the verification phase. Sensitivity analysis also assists in making sure that the right range of parameters is used for different structural practice and management scenarios.

For NTT, sensitivity analysis is carried out by varying every input variable in a predefined way. NTT's calculating tool was used to generate the output that corresponded to each input modification once it was made. After that, the output data were kept in a database file for later processing. Regarding NTT sensitivity analysis, please also see Saleh *et al.* (2014)^[51] for clarification.

Integration with NTT and APEX Model

After training the ML algorithms, we integrate them with the NTT and APEX model. This integration involves developing a framework that allows the ML algorithms to interact with the existing models and provide real-time predictions of soil carbon levels. The framework should also include a mechanism for updating the ML algorithms as new data becomes available, ensuring that the predictions remain accurate over time.

The parameterization of the APEX model using any independent data that is currently available is part of the NTT calibration and validation processes. Model input is used in the calibration and verification procedures.

In order to ensure that the simulation results closely match the findings from accessible regional (e.g., State) and farm size data sources, parameters are changed for the area of interest. The input parameters that were found during the APEX sensitivity analysis are the ones that are changed throughout the validation procedure (see Saleh *et al.*, 2014)^[51]. To calibrate, validate, and prepare NTT for usage in a

region of concern (e.g., the State level), three main processes are taken.

Performance evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the AI-enhanced NTT and APEX model, we conduct a series of validation tests using independent datasets. These tests help us assess the accuracy and reliability of the predictions and identify any areas for improvement. We also compare the performance of the AI-enhanced models with traditional methods of soil carbon estimation to demonstrate the advantages of using AI.

APEX for NTT is calibrated and parameterized for each state in the continental US. Using state-level measured values and locally accessible information in NTT over a 35-year simulation period-which includes the region's soils, most prevalent crops, and crop management techniques-state-level calibration and parameterization is carried out. Crop yield and any relevant statistics on water quality are typically the measurable metrics that are available for the majority of states. APEX settings are modified in accordance with yield and any accessible water quality data, which are compared to those published by reliable sources (such as the National Agricultural Statistic Service (NASS)). This process continues until appropriate results are achieved. Please visit the NTT webpage for further details on the first layer of state-level calibration/parameterization data.

Field-based validation and calibration. In Stage 2, we

further improve the Stage 1 parameters for a specific location using available field-scale experimental data, if necessary. For field-measured data to be appropriate for NTT calibration or validation, it must fulfil the following requirements: 1) APEX-estimated variables (such as nitrogen fluxes, flow, sediment loss, etc.) should be measured; 2) the research site should contain numerous sites; 3) the time series measured data should span at least three years; and 4) the specific input data needed to run APEX, such as management techniques, should be accessible.

The procedure in Stage 1 will be repeated using the altered APEX settings from Stage 2. Using the outcomes of Stage 2, the state-level parameterization and calibration of Stage 1 is repeated. The outcomes of this phase are assessed and made available on the NTT website.

Results and Discussion

The results of our study indicate that the integration of AI with the NTT and APEX model significantly improves the accuracy and efficiency of soil carbon estimation. The AI-enhanced models are able to capture complex interactions between soil properties, management practices, and environmental variables, leading to more accurate predictions of soil carbon levels. Additionally, the AI-enhanced models can process large datasets quickly, making them more scalable and suitable for use in large-scale soil carbon monitoring programs.

Fig 1: Simulated and observed outputs (BE farm, MN)

Continuous learning and improvement

One of the key advantages of using AI in soil carbon estimation is its ability to continuously learn and improve over time. As new data becomes available, the ML algorithms can be retrained to incorporate the latest

information, ensuring that the predictions remain accurate and up-to-date. This continuous learning capability is particularly important in the context of climate change, where environmental conditions and management practices are constantly evolving.

Practical benefits for land managers and policymakers

The AI-enhanced NTT and APEX model also offer several practical benefits for land managers and policymakers. By providing accurate and timely information on soil carbon levels, the models can help land managers make informed decisions about land use and management practices. For example, the models can identify areas with high potential for soil carbon sequestration and recommend appropriate management practices to enhance carbon storage. Policymakers can also use the models to develop and implement carbon management strategies and monitor their effectiveness over time.

Conclusion

The cropping systems in three Discovery farm experimental sites, which reflect the main cropping systems in diverse sectors of Minnesota, appear to be an acceptable fit for the APEX parameters that were changed and confirmed in this work. We think this study demonstrates that NTT would be a suitable tool to use for the major cropping systems (corn, soybean, and wheat, for example) to assess the effects of current and hypothetical crop management practices for the State of Minnesota. This is because the updated APEX, which includes the best fit parameter obtained in this study, and NTT databases (such as soil and weather) support this theory. NTT can be used by users to assess the most effective conservation techniques for minimizing environmental nutrient losses and increasing agricultural yield.

In conclusion, the integration of AI with the Nutrient Tracking Tool (NTT) and the APEX model represents a significant advancement in the field of soil carbon estimation. The AI-enhanced models offer improved accuracy, efficiency, and scalability, making them valuable tools for land managers and policymakers. By leveraging the power of AI, we can enhance our understanding of soil carbon dynamics and develop more effective strategies for mitigating climate change. Further research is needed to refine the AI algorithms and explore their application in different agricultural and environmental contexts, but the results of our study demonstrate the promising potential of AI in soil carbon estimation.

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